

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTONATION IN THE STYLISTIC DIFFERENTIATION OF ORAL TEXTS

Rakhimova Gavhar Jamshid kizi

Karshi State University

Master's 2nd stage student

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Abstract. *It is known that descriptive phonetics refers to phonetic phenomena such as speech sounds, their formation, types, changes, syllables, intonation, pause, stress, and their peculiarities. These phenomena recorded in the process of speech combine into a single system and form a speech act.*

Key words: *phonostylistics, denotation, connotation, intonation, rhythm, pause, stress, syntagma, emphasis, emotional-expressiveness.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИНТОНАЦИИ В СТИЛИСТИЧЕСКОЙ ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЦИИ УСТНЫХ ТЕКСТОВ

Аннотация. *Известно, что описательная фонетика относится к таким фонетическим явлениям, как звуки речи, их образование, виды, изменения, слоги, интонация, пауза, ударение и их особенности. Эти явления, зафиксированные в процессе речи, объединяются в единую систему и образуют речевой акт.*

Ключевые слова: *фоностилистика, денотат, коннотация, интонация, ритм, пауза, ударение, синтагма, акцент, эмоционально-выразительность.*

Intonation is a complex unity of prosodic features of speech: melody (voice pitch); Sentence stress; temporal characteristics (duration, tempo, pause); rhythm; wood (voice quality). The term "prosody" is widely used in linguistic literature along with the term "intonation", but in a broad sense. Intonation organizes a sentence, determines the communicative types of sentences and subordinate clauses, divides sentences into intonational groups, highlights words and phrases, expresses oppositions and relationships. There are no sentences without a certain intonation, and without it we cannot express any meaning.

Intonation can be described at the acoustic level (in terms of its acoustic characteristics), at the perceptual level (in terms of the characteristics perceived by the human ear), and at the linguistic level (in terms of the meanings expressed by intonation). There are different approaches to describing intonation and different definitions of this phenomenon. Intonation at the perceptual level is defined as a complex formed by significant changes in pitch, volume and tempo (rate of speech and pauses), closely related to each other. There are definitions that include timbre, which some linguists sometimes consider as the fourth component of intonation (it shows the speaker's emotions, such as joy, sadness, irony, anger, indignation, etc.). In the British and American tradition, intonation is limited only to changes in pitch (tone). Intonation is identified with sound movements (melody), since pitch has the greatest linguistic significance. There are different ways of indicating intonation, but the most striking are staves (two horizontal parallel lines indicating the approximate upper and lower limits of the vocal pitch range in speech) with dots, dashes and curves (which correspond to unstressed and stressed syllables within the vocal range) located at

different levels, and tonic symbols (used in the line of text itself). They are widely used in textbooks.

The components of intonation can be considered at the acoustic level. Each of them has its own acoustic correlate and can be objectively measured. Pitch correlates with the frequency of vibrations of the vocal cords, volume - with intensity, tempo - with the time (duration) during which a speech unit lasts. Pitch is usually described as a system of tones (lower, higher, lower-higher, etc.), pitch levels (keys, registers), which can be high, medium, and low, and pitch ranges (intervals between the highest and lowest level). tonal syllables), which can be wide, normal and narrow.

The basic unit of intonation is the intonation pattern: tonal movements (which are inextricably linked to changes in volume) and tempo. Intonation patterns serve to actualize syntagmas in oral speech. A syntagma (semantic group) is a group of words that is semantically and syntactically complete. In phonetics, actualized syntagms are called intonation groups. Each intonation group may consist of one or more potential syntagmas. For example, the sentence "I think he will come soon" has two potential syntagms: "I think" and "He will come soon." A phrase (a sentence implemented in oral speech) may contain one or more intonation groups. The number of intonation groups depends on the length of the phrase and the semantic meaning given to various parts of the phrase: This 'bed `didn't sleep`.

Intonation comes from Latin which means to pronounce aloud. Intonation which serves to express the syntactic meanings and emotional-expressive colors of speech demonstrates rhythmic-melodic side, high-low volume and tone[1]. The following are the constituent elements of intonation: 1) speech melody; 2) rhythm of speech; 3) speech intensity; 4) speech tempo; 5) timbre of speech; 6) logical and phrase emphasis. Apparently, intonation is a phonostylistic phenomenon consisting of a complicated complex associated with speech pronunciation. While making some research on intonation it is vitally important to make some comments about 1) speech speed; 2) speech tone; 3) pauses in the sentence.

Speech speed is determined by the time spent on the sounds in the speech process during its pronunciation. The speed of each part of speech varies in its different communicative forms. In particular, the subject given at the beginning of the affirmative sentence begins more slowly than the speed of the general sentence. As the speed shifts to the predicate, it accelerates and reaches a maximum. The speed of the passages in the interrogative sentences is slightly higher than the speed of the affirmative sentences. Exclamatory sentences are pronounced aloud because they have an exciting sense. Speech tone is a system of high or low pronunciation of syllables in a sentence. Volume is measured in hertz. The communicative types of speech vary in tone. Our thoughts and feelings also reach our interlocutor through sound, that is, tone. In speech, words are said with a certain intonation, the speech pronounced without excitement, without tone and without feeling at all becomes dull and boring. There are two tones in speech: a rising tone and falling tone. A falling tone signifies the completion of a sentence whereas in the rising tone, meanings such as surprise, protest, resistance are expressed. Therefore, intonation has the following types of interrogative, exclamatory, calling, completed, modal, unfinished, low, high, flat, strong.

In Uzbek linguistics, the phenomenon of intonation has not been specifically studied. No fundamental scientific work has been created. Some textbooks and manuals on phonetics and

stylistics contain only some ideas and comments along the way. However, the merits of Professor A. Gulyamov in this regard are enormous. For the first time in Uzbek linguistics, Professor A. Gulyamov expressed his scientific views on intonation, its components and functions, and its relationship with syntax. He proved with examples that intonation is one of the necessary elements of speech. Professor A. Gulyamov also gave a detailed explanation of the syntagma, which is inextricably linked with intonation. It is a speech element between two pauses, a phonetic integrity that represents a whole and called it a group that is structurally and semantically integrated within a sentence. He writes: "Intonation is the syntactic division of a group of words in a sentence, how the elements are connected. As long as there is an intonational change in a group, it usually indicates a syntactic division, a difference in meaning. For example: 1) Katta mevali (daraxt) (the tree has big fruit) - 2) katta (mevali daraxt) (tree is large)

In some works, however, the exact pronunciation of foreign language words is used to express the spirit of that period in the speech of the characters. As noted above, one of the supersegment elements in speech is the pause, which is to some extent related to intonation. But a pause has logical-grammatical and stylistic possibilities because it is an experience associated with the cessation, interruption of the flow of speech with different goals and tasks, and the feeling that realizes a more subjective relationship. It is used for physiological and psychological reasons, for the purpose of distinguishing pronunciation of sentences and syntagma, as well as for enumerating organized parts to emphasize separated parts.

Now, if we think about direct syllabic, it is close to the truth to say that syllabic can be not only a segment but also a supersegment (aspects related to pronunciation) from a stylistic point of view. Because in order to realistically reflect the connotative meaning associated with the pronunciation of certain words, they are pronounced and written in syllables. Thus, the use of intonation in Uzbek and English literary works can serve as an important stylistic device for showing some meanings such as love, affection, amazement, surprise, confidence, indifference, care, attention, fear, horror, discomfort, sorrow, mental anguish, anger and express state of protagonists of the work without using some parts of speech.

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